

Spurious Self-Suppression Method: Application to TM Cavity Filters

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Abstract— This paper presents a new approach for improving spurious free band in filters. The main idea is to control the coupling coefficients of the spurious resonances, in order to force them to cancel each other. This approach is completely different from the classical one where all couplings are minimized in order to excite as less as possible the spurious resonances. In fact, in this approach all spurious couplings are maximized except the central coupling that is instead minimized. This method is first explained in terms of equivalent circuits. Then, in order to show its applicability to real microwave filters, it is applied to the TM cavity filters and used to remove both spurious resonances due to higher order cavity modes and to TE₁₀ mode of coupling irises. Design examples of 4th and 6th order TM cavity filters are presented. With respect to the classical TM cavity filter, where the first spurious appears around 11.4 GHz, the TM filters designed by exploiting the self-suppression method present spurious free bands up to 20.2 GHz (20 GHz for 6th order filter), improving the filter response up to 2.2 times the center frequency of 9.2 GHz. Another advantage is that, in contrast to the classical spurious suppression method that does not allow responses with TZs in TM filters, the self-suppression method allows for a number of TZs equal to N-2 (N being the filter order) and it also allow a certain control of their position.

Index Terms—Coupling values, higher order modes, microwave filters, spurious resonances, self-suppression, transverse magnetic (TM) cavity, transmission zeros (TZs).

I. INTRODUCTION

RECENT growth in technological advancement demands compact and high-performance microwave/millimeter wave components especially for satellite payload communication system. To reduce the cost and volume of the overall payload communication system, components with small size are required. Being one of the bulkiest parts in satellite transceivers, the miniaturization of filters is often a desired requirement [1], [2]. Due to its low loss, high quality (Q) factor and high-power handling capability, waveguide technology has been widely used in microwave and millimeter wave communication systems. Passband filters often suffer

from spurious resonances that limit the wideness of their stopband. Wider stopbands are obtained by cascading a low pass filter to a passband filter. The advantage of having a passband filter with a wide spurious free stopband is that it allows avoiding the use of low pass or at least it allows using a less bulky one, thus reducing weight and volume of overall payload communication system which strongly impacts on the overall cost [3], [4].

Different techniques have been proposed for increasing the stopband performance in microwave filters. In [5], wide stopband in waveguide filters is achieved by using Stepped Impedance Resonators (SIRs). Authors in [6], proposed the use of resonators with different transversal dimensions to control spurious resonances in rectangular waveguide filters. In [7], the integration of low pass filter with bandpass filter for improving stopband performance is proposed. A compact waveguide filter using capacitively loaded cavity with improved stopband response is proposed in [8]. Mushroom shaped posts are used in [9], [10] for improving the stopband characteristic in combline filters. The use of capacitive irises to improve stopband performance can be found in [11].

Another classical and intuitive approach consists in avoiding the excitation of the spurious resonances by minimizing (possibly zeroing) their coupling coefficients [12]. The limitation of this approach is that, in some cases, coupling values can be minimized but not avoided (e.g., because of manufacturing tolerances) and this may result in narrowband spurious and stopband performance degradation.

Other different approaches for stopband performance improvement in microwave bandpass filters using microstrip and Substrate Integrated Waveguide (SIW) technology have been reported in [13] - [22]. In [13], SIR based approach is used in planar filter configuration to achieve wider stopband. Microstrip bandpass filter with ultra-wide stopband is reported in [14]. Authors in [15], proposes multilayer SIW filter with proper coupling position to suppress higher order modes. Quite similar approach is adopted in [16], to suppress neighboring mode to improve out-of-band response. A method similar to that presented in [12] for waveguide technology has been reported in [17], [18] for SIW technology. However, due to lossy nature of SIW technology, it is easy to suppress spurious (due to losses in dielectric material), if it appears as a very narrow parasitic band, as it is generally the case when spurious coupling values are minimized as much as possible. Other SIW based approaches can be found in [19] - [22].

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Recently, some articles studied the way to improve the out-of-band behavior of SIR based filters, but this was only for wideband application, and it resulted in an increased geometrical complexity [23] - [25].

Several articles have been published that exploit the concept of non-resonating nodes (NRNs) along with resonating modes to realize transmission zeros (TZs) and to achieve better selectivity and better stopband performance in waveguide filters [26], [27]. This method has been also applied to TM cavity filters that allows designing filter with reduced length [28]. Indeed, TM cavity filters represents an excellent compromise when very compact structures with reasonably high Q factors are required [29] - [32]. Generalized study about TM dual mode cavity filters has been presented in [33] and [34]. Improvement of the out-of-band behavior in TM dual-mode cavities is presented in [35] by using circular TM cavities and multiple-aperture irises.

In this paper, a new method for the self-suppression of spurious resonances through the control of the spurious coupling arrangement is presented. The method is first presented at equivalent circuit level. In order to demonstrate their applicability to real microwave filters, the method has been applied in the improvement of the out-of-band performance in TM cavity filters. The proposed technique consists in forcing the spurious resonances to cancel each other. In contrast to the classical approach, where all the coupling values to spurious resonances are minimized, in the proposed method all spurious couplings except the central one are maximized. The central one is instead minimized (or zeroed when possible). The basic idea of the self-suppression approach has been reported in [36], where it has been applied to a second order TM cavity filter. This paper further extends the study of the proposed method to higher (even) order TM cavity filters. With respect to [36], where only spurious frequencies due to cavity higher order modes have been removed, this paper also shows the method for removing spurious frequencies due to the coupling irises. Detailed analysis has been presented in this paper for removing spurious frequencies due to irises as well as higher order TM_{120} and TM_{210} cavity modes. Design examples of 4th and 6th order TM cavity filters are presented. Furthermore, the proposed approach for spurious suppression is compared to the classical one [12], [17], [18] in which all couplings to spurious resonances are minimized. Results shows the feasibility of the proposed approach, which offers better spurious suppression performance. Moreover, in the specific application to TM filters, the proposed method allows for a better control on the band selectivity. Indeed, in contrast to the classical spurious suppression method where TZs completely disappear, by using the proposed self-suppression method N-2 TZs are still allowed (being N the filter order) and their position can be still controlled. In order to demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed approach, several 4th and 6th order TM cavity filters have been designed. Finally, a 6th order filter has been manufactured and measured. Good agreement between simulation and measured results has been obtained.

This paper is organized as follows. In Section II, coupling theory and band suppression of both even and odd order bands are discussed. In Section III, 4th order TM cavity filter designs

exploiting classical design approaches are presented. In Section IV, design examples of 4th and 6th order TM cavity filters with the proposed spurious self-suppression approach is presented. In Section V, measurement result of 6th order filter is presented. The conclusion is drawn in Section VI.

II. SPURIOUS SELF-SUPPRESSION METHOD

Microwave filters are obtained by cascading resonators that resonate in the filter band. The desired passband is obtained by properly selecting all coupling values. In some cases, however resonators can produce spurious modes that resonates at different frequencies producing spurious bands. Filter bands and spurious bands are conceptually similar, the only difference is that spurious bands are undesired. In this paper, it is shown a new method for eliminating (or better saying to strongly attenuate) the undesired bands. The method is slightly different in case of even order and odd order response. Both of them will be shown in the following.

A. Self-Suppression of Even Order Parasitic Band

The classical method used for the parasitic band cancellation [12] is to minimize all couplings. Of course, this method works very well if we are able to set all couplings to zero. However, in many practical cases it is not possible and the best thing we can do is minimize all couplings. In such case, much better results are obtained by using the self-cancellation method where only the central coupling is minimized whereas all other are maximized.

In order to show how the self-suppression method works, the four-pole configuration of Fig. 1a is considered. The relevant response is shown in Fig. 1b in the case of all identical coupling values ($M_{S1}=M_{12}=M_{23}=0.5$). As shown in Fig. 2, when the central coupling M_{23} decreases, the band attenuation increases. In the same figure, the response obtained reducing all couplings is also shown. As can be seen in that case spurious frequencies have not been eliminated.

Fig. 1. Four-pole configuration. (a) Coupling routing scheme. (b) S parameters response.

Fig. 2. Passband response. Band suppression obtained by decreasing M_{23} .

This method works for all even order structures (2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12 ...) only, and it is based on a sort of self-suppression in which resonances cancel one another. The mechanism allowing the self-cancellation can be explained by using the transversal topology. According to the theory explained in [37], it is possible to transform an inline topology into a transversal topology. In the case of 4th order filter, the inline structure of Fig. 1a can be transformed into the transversal topology of Fig. 3a. In contrast with the inline topology where all resonators resonate at the same frequency (e.g. Chebyshev response), in the transversal topology resonators must work at different frequencies, otherwise they cancel one another destroying the response. By the way, such resonance frequencies correspond to the reflection zeros (RZs) of the response, as shown in Fig. 1b. The cancellation is due to the fact that the output couplings of resonators have alternating signs, as shown in Fig. 3a. This cancellation is the one exploited in the proposed self-cancellation method. Indeed, the decrease of the central coupling value in the inline configuration corresponds to a reduction of the frequency separation between the two consecutive resonators f_i and f_{i+1} , with $i = 1,3,5...$. For the 4th order filter, this means that frequency f_1 became closer to f_2 and frequency f_3 became closer to f_4 . This can be clearly seen from Fig. 3b.

From the point of view of the response this means that when the couple of RZs becoming closer, it passes from imaginary axis to the complex plane thus resulting in a couple of conjugated zeros. This suggests that in case, we would like to synthesize a bandpass exploiting the self-suppression method, we have to impose RZs in the complex plane. This cancellation, explained above at the level of routing scheme, has a very clear physical meaning when a full-wave structure is considered. As an example, the structure of Fig. 4 consisting of cavities connected through irises is considered. When the inline model is considered, each resonator of the routing scheme corresponds to the resonant mode of a single isolated cavity. When instead the transversal model is considered, each resonator of the routing scheme corresponds to a resonant mode (eigenmode) of the whole physical structure, as shown in Fig. 4. Such eigenmodes can be easily found by using a full wave simulator. According to Fig. 4, all four eigenmodes can be seen as a combination of cavity modes that can have phase equal 0 deg. or equal 180 deg. As an example, the mode

resonating at the lower frequency f_1 consists in the field configuration where all resonant modes of the cavities have the same phase (0 deg.). The second mode resonating at f_2 consists instead in the first two cavity modes with phase 0 deg. and the last two with phase 180 deg. etc. Note that all eigenmodes have phase equal 0 deg. at the input (corresponding to the source), while the output (corresponding to the load) the phase is 0 deg. for the first and third eigenmode and 180 deg. for the second and fourth. This is consistent with the sign of the coupling in the routing scheme of Fig. 3a. These different signs at the output of the eigenmodes allows the cancellation of eigenmodes resonating at f_1 and f_2 and eigenmodes resonating at f_3 and f_4 when the central coupling tends to zero.

Fig. 3. Four pole filter. (a) Transversal topology. (b) Self-cancellation of resonances when M_{23} decreases.

Fig. 4. E-field distribution at the frequency of the reflection zeros.

B. Self-Suppression of Odd Order Parasitic Band

According to Fig. 5a, in case of odd order bands there is no central coupling as the number of coupling coefficients is even. This means that odd order bands have two central couplings (M_{12} and M_{23} in case of Fig. 5a). Of course, our aim is to deal with a symmetric structure where $|M_{i,j}| = |M_{N+1-j,N+1-i}|$ (being N the filter order), because symmetric structures are much easier to manage and to design. In the case of Fig. 5a, this means that M_{12} must be equal to M_{23} . As a consequence, the strategy of minimizing the central coupling corresponds to the minimization of $M_{12} = M_{23}$. Unfortunately, as shown in Fig. 5b for $M_{12} = M_{23} = 0.05$, this strategy does not work. However, as shown in Fig. 5c, the strategy works by detuning the resonance frequency of the central resonator so that it resonates far away from the parasitic band. This figure shows what happens to the response of Fig. 5b when the resonance frequency of the central resonator is increased. As can be seen, once the resonance frequency of the central resonator is increased and it goes out of the parasitic band range, the remaining RZs starts attenuating by suppressing one another. The only visible resonance remains that of the central resonator R2, but it can be pushed outside of the spurious free band required by the specifications. To understand how this mechanism works, we can consider that the frequency shifted resonator behaves as a coupling structure between its previous and its next resonator. Considering the initial equivalent circuit of Fig. 6a, after detuning R2, the equivalent circuit became that of Fig. 6b where the cascade of M_{12} , R2 and M_{23} have been substituted by a single impedance inverter M'_{12} . Of course, this new equivalent circuit allows a good approximation of the response in the parasitic band but does not take into account the resonance of R2 far away from the parasitic band. Now the parasitic band is again an even order band, and the self-suppression method can be applied by decreasing M'_{12} . The larger the frequency shift of R2, the smaller the M'_{12} . This explains the attenuation of the parasitic band of Fig. 5b. Another way to reduce M'_{12} is also by reducing M_{12} and M_{23} .

Fig. 5. Third order filter. (a) Filter response with normalized coupling values. (b) Minimizing two central coupling values, $M_{12}=M_{23}=0.05$. (c) Band suppression by minimizing M_{12} ($M_{s1}=0.5$, $M_{12}=M_{23}=0.05$) and increasing resonance frequency of central resonator (R2).

Fig. 6. Third order filter. (a) Equivalent circuit. (b) Equivalent circuit after increasing the resonance frequency of central resonator (R2).

In order to demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed methods, in Section IV the two strategies discussed above have been applied to TM cavity filters for removing their parasitic bands due to higher order modes (even order) and coupling iris resonances (odd order).

III. CLASSICAL TM CAVITY FILTER DESIGN

In single mode TM cavity filters, TM_{110} modes are exploited as resonant modes to generate the filter passband. Higher order cavity resonant modes TM_{120} and the resonance of the fundamental mode of coupling irises (TE_{10}) are instead responsible for undesired parasitic bands. The classical TM

Fig. 7. TM cavity. (a) 3-D view of the cavity along with input and output irises. (b) Magnetic field distribution of the fundamental mode TM_{110} . (c) Magnetic field distribution of the TM_{120} mode.

cavity [28], is sketched in Fig. 7, together with the field distribution of the fundamental mode TM_{110} , and of the higher order mode TM_{120} . The configuration of 4 pole single mode TM cavity filter is shown in Fig. 8a, along with the dimensions. The filter is fed through standard $wr-90$ waveguide. Fig. 8b shows the relevant routing scheme including filter passband (TM_{110}), filter parasitic band due to higher order modes (TM_{120}) and filter parasitic band due to coupling iris resonances (TE_{10}) mode. Considering that all irises are horizontally positioned, the TM_{210} mode is not excited, and it does not contribute to the parasitic bands. For the filter passband a routing scheme with NRNs has been considered. This configuration allows taking into account the bypass coupling of each single cavity (dotted lines) generated by the non-resonating mode TE_{101} [28], [29]. The total number of TZs of the filter is equal to the number of cavities where the bypass coupling is not zero [28], [29].

Fig. 8c shows the response of a classical 4 pole TM cavity filter, where no procedures for improving the out-of-band behavior have been considered. The filter band is centered at 9.2 GHz with a fractional bandwidth (FBW) of 1.3%. Four TZs are present at the lower stopband as a consequence of the cross-couplings generated by the non-resonant TE_{101} cavity modes [28]. As can be seen, some parasitic bands degrade the out-of-band performance of the filter. In particular, the parasitic band around 12 GHz is due to the coupling iris resonances, while that around 16 GHz is generated by the higher order modes TM_{120} . It should be noted that, iris 1 (and iris 5) does not produce resonances (at least not at the frequency of the other irises) and it only contribute, together with the first cavity, to the impedance inverter connecting source to iris 2 resonance (and load to iris 4 resonance in case of iris 5). For that reason, only the 3 resonances due to irises 2,3,4 are visible in Fig. 8c.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 8. TM cavity filter. (a) 3-D view, filter dimensions, $w_1=13.5$ mm, $w_2=11.9$ mm, $w_3=11.46$ mm, $h_1=2.6$ mm, $h_2=2.6$ mm, $h_3=1.5$ mm, $l=5$ mm, $w_{c1}=22.69$ mm, $h_{c1}=22.68$ mm, $w_{c2}=22.75$ mm, $h_{c2}=22.75$ mm, $p=3.05$ mm (p is the distance of irises from the cavity center). (b) Routing scheme including filter passband (TM_{110}), filter parasitic band (TM_{120}), and iris resonances (TE_{10}). (c) Response of the 4th order classical TM cavity filter. The out-of-band response shows iris resonance parasitic band and TM_{120} mode parasitic band. The figure inset shows the zoomed passband.

A. Classical Approach for Removing Higher Order Modes Spurious Frequencies

The classical approach for eliminating parasitic bands consists in the minimization of all possible couplings to higher order modes generating the parasitic band. As an example, this technique has been applied in [12]. In case of TM filters, according to Fig. 8a, the best way for decreasing as much as possible all the coupling between higher order modes on adjacent cavities is to alternate the iris orientation from horizontal to vertical. This is shown in Fig. 9a. Indeed, according to Fig. 7, because of the field distribution of the fundamental resonant TM_{110} mode, its coupling does not depend on the iris orientation [33]. This means that the filter passband is not influenced by the orientation. Something different happens instead to the higher order modes: the first horizontal iris excites the TM_{120} spurious mode, but the second (vertical) iris does not excite the TM_{120} mode and so on [33]. Actually, the coupling to TM_{120} modes obtained by a vertical iris is very small, but it is not zero. This small residual coupling is responsible for the spurious frequencies around 15/16 GHz shown in the response of the Fig. 9b. Of course, this response is much better than that in Fig. 8c, where no strategies for

Fig. 9. TM filter after the application of the classical spurious suppression method. (a) 3-D view of the filter. (b) Wideband filter response.

removing spurious frequencies was taken into account. However, some spurious frequencies are still present. Actually, vertical irises may also excite the TM_{210} mode thus creating additional spurious resonances around 16 GHz. However, in the response of Fig. 9b, these resonances have been removed by placing vertical irises in a specific position from the cavity center where TM_{210} mode has the minimum of the magnetic field. This corresponds to a distance from the center equal to a quarter of the cavity size ($w/4$) [33]. In order to reach this new position, the distance of the vertical irises from the center has been increased. This results in an undesired increase of the coupling M_{12} that ruins the filter response. In order to recover the original M_{12} value, iris size w_2 has been reduced. As a result, two iris resonances initially present around 12 GHz are now shifted to higher frequency around 17.8 GHz.

IV. FILTERS WITH SPURIOUS SELF-SUPPRESSION APPROACH

According to the theory discussed in Section II, the application of the strategy for the spurious self-suppression to TM filters can be summarized into the following three steps:

1) **Central iris orthogonally positioned.**

When the central iris is orthogonally placed with respect to all other irises, the central coupling coefficient of the higher order mode parasitic band is dramatically reduced. This results in the parasitic band attenuation.

- 2) **Central iris positioned far away from the cavity center.** This allows for the reduction of the central iris width (w_3) thus increasing its resonance frequency. This leads to the attenuation of the iris parasitic band.
- 3) **All irises (except the central one) positioned close to the cavity center.** This increases all couplings in the higher mode parasitic band except the central one. This results in the improvement of the suppression of the higher order mode parasitic band.

Note that, according to Fig. 10a, the distance p_x of the iris from the cavity center is here used to remove parasitic bands. In [28], the same parameters are used for controlling the TZs. This means that in spurious self-suppression method, the control of TZs is a little bit more limited. However, in contrast to the classical approach of Fig. 9 where TZs completely disappear, in filter designs using spurious self-suppression method, a certain control capability of the TZs still remains, as shown later on.

A. 4th Order Filter

The three steps described above are here applied to the 4th order TM cavity filter of Fig. 8, starting from the central iris rotation.

Central iris orthogonally positioned. The four-pole filter of Fig. 8, after its central iris has been vertically positioned, is shown in Fig. 10a. and Fig. 10b. Its response is shown in Fig. 10c.

In theory, according to the modal field distribution of Fig. 7b, the central coupling between fundamental modes TM_{110} (M_{23}) does not change when the iris is rotated by 90 deg. if the same distance p_x from the center and the same size w_3 are maintained. However, in practice a small readjustment is necessary for reobtaining the desired filter passband ($p_x = 2.55$ mm, $w_3 = 10.85$ mm).

In theory, according to Fig. 7c, the central coupling M_{23}^{pm} between TM_{120} modes of cavity 2 and 3 is zero. In practice, because of the presence of irises 3 and 4 that perturbs the fields in cavity 2 and 3, it is very small, and it allows, according to the spurious self-suppression method, a strong attenuation of the parasitic band due to the TM_{120} modes. However, a spurious frequency related to the TM_{210} mode is now present at 16.2 GHz, as can be seen in Fig. 10c. This is because the vertical position of iris 3 allows the excitation of the TM_{210} mode. Fig. 11 shows the magnetic field of TM_{210} mode calculated at 16.2 GHz.

Finally, as a side effect of the central iris rotation, the resonances of iris 2 and 4 are strongly attenuated (about 18 dB). This is because the iris 3 rotation in some way starts the procedure described in Section II.B related to the suppression of parasitic odd order bands when the central resonator is pushed out-of-band. Indeed, in this case iris 3 resonates at slightly higher frequency with respect to iris 2 and 4, and the rotation of iris 3, strongly decreases the coupling between iris 2 and 4 resonances, thus resulting in a strong attenuation of the parasitic band generated by iris 2 and iris 4. Of course, iris 3 resonance is still present at 12.6 GHz, but according to the method described in Section II.B, it must be pushed at much higher frequency. This is what is done in the next step.

Fig. 10. Four-pole TM cavity filter with the central iris rotated. (a) Iris 3 front view. (b) Filter 3-D view. (c) Wideband response.

Fig. 11. H field of TM_{210} mode at 16.2 GHz.

Central iris positioned far away from the cavity center. Considering the field distribution in Fig. 7b, the higher the distance of the iris from the center, the higher the coupling between resonating modes. This means that, for maintaining the same coupling level M_{23} , the iris width w_3 must be decreased when the distance from the center increases. This is illustrated in Fig. 12a, where the curve shows the value of p_x that shall be selected for each value of iris width w_3 to maintain the value of the coupling $M_{23}=0.0087$ corresponding to the value obtained from the filter synthesis.

In order to remove the odd order parasitic band, we apply the strategy illustrated in Section II.B consisting in the increasing of the resonant frequency of the central iris (iris 3).

This can be done by decreasing the iris width w_3 . By exploiting the graph of Fig. 12a we can select the iris position p_x that allows maintaining the filter band unchanged. In other words, the application of the strategy illustrated in Section II.B consists in the decreasing of w_3 and in the increasing of p_x according to Fig. 12a.

The last thing to check is the effect of decreasing w_3 and increasing p_x in the coupling between higher order modes TM_{210} . This is well explained in [33] and [34]. In contrast to what happens to the coupling between fundamental modes TM_{110} that increases when p_x increases, the coupling between TM_{210} modes decreases reaching zero at $p_x = w/4 = 5.6875$ mm where, according to Fig. 11, its H-field is zero. This effect, combined with the iris width reduction, allows a strong reduction of the coupling between TM_{210} higher order modes. The coupling M_{23}^{pm} between the TM_{120} mode in the two central cavities has been strongly decreased by rotating the central iris. However, the reduction of iris width contributes to a further reduction of the residual coupling due to the presence of the iris that breaks the symmetry of the field distribution.

In conclusion, in order to mitigate both the odd order parasitic band due to iris resonances and the parasitic band due to higher order modes TM_{120}/TM_{210} the iris width w_3 must be decreased and the position p_x must be increased according to Fig. 12a.

The above-described effects can be clearly seen in the full wave response of Fig. 12b, where this phenomenon has been shown in four steps (#1, #2, #3, #4) corresponding to the four curves related to different central iris widths ($w_3 = 10.85$ mm; 9.15 mm; 7.2 mm; 6.5 mm). In order to maintain the same response in the filter band, the corresponding values of iris offset $p_x = 2.55$ mm; 3.6 mm; 5.6875 mm; 7 mm have been selected according to Fig. 12a. The step #1 ($w_3 = 10.85$ mm, $p_x = 2.55$ mm) is that of Fig. 10c. According to Fig. 12b, decreasing iris 3 width w_3 , its resonance frequency increases, assuming the values of 12.6 GHz; 13.9 GHz; 18.5 GHz; 20.3 GHz. At the same time the attenuation of the iris parasitic band at 12.25 GHz is increased, passing from less than 18 dB of Fig. 10c to about 35 dB. As can be seen in the zoomed part of the graph in Fig. 12b, the central iris width reduction also has two additional desired effects: the increment of the attenuation of the TM_{120} mode parasitic band (because of the decreasing of the M_{23}^{pm}) and the cancellation of the TM_{210} mode spurious resonance starting from step #3.

Fig. 12. Four pole Filter (a) Relation of p_x and w_3 giving a constant value of coupling $M_{23}=0.0087$ (b) Effect of position p_x and size w_3 on parasitic bands. The parasitic band related to the higher order modes has been zoomed.

It should be noted that, position p_x changes the resonance frequency of the TM_{210} mode. When the resonance frequency of the TM_{210} mode reaches the higher parasitic band of TM_{120} modes, it cooperates with TM_{120} modes in reinforcing that parasitic band. This is what happens in step #2. However, keep decreasing the iris 3 width w_3 (steps #2 and #3) and increasing p_x the resonance frequency of TM_{210} mode arrives outside the TM_{120} mode parasitic band and the problem disappears.

Fig. 13 shows the response of the filter obtained with $w_3 = 6.5$ mm and $p_x = 7$ mm, that shows the iris parasitic band suppression of about 32 dB and higher order TM_{120} spurious modes suppression of 25 dB.

Fig. 13. Filter response with iris placed at a position $p_x = 7$ mm and size $w_3 = 6.5$ mm.

All irises (except the central one) positioned close to the cavity center. For an efficient suppression of the higher order mode parasitic band, in addition to the central coupling minimization obtained through the previous steps, the maximization of all other coupling values can be exploited. The maximization of the couplings between TM_{120} modes is obtained by shifting the irises close to the cavity center and at the same time by increasing the iris width in order to recover the original coupling between fundamental TM_{110} modes. This can be clearly seen in Fig. 14b where different curves for different value of the iris offsets p_1 and p_2 shown in Fig. 14a are plotted. The blue curve is the response of the structure suggested by the classical philosophy of reducing as much as possible the couplings to the spurious modes. Indeed, the central coupling has been already minimized by rotating the central iris, all other couplings are instead minimized when iris 1 and iris 2 are positioned halfway between the cavity center and the cavity side ($p_1 = h_{c1}/4 = 5.5$ mm and $p_2 = h_{c2}/4 = 5.635$ mm). In theory, this position guarantees zero coupling between TM_{120} modes. In practice, the coupling is very low (but not zero) and the parasitic band due to TM_{120} modes is very narrowband but unfortunately it reaches 0 dB, thus again demonstrating the weakness of the classical approach. The highest suppression of the parasitic band is instead related to the red curve obtained with the lower values of p_1 and p_2 ($p_1 = 3$ mm and $p_2 = 3$ mm) that maximizes couplings to TM_{120} spurious modes.

Fig. 14. Effect of iris offsets on filter response. (a) Four pole TM cavity filter. (b) Filter response.

Fig. 15. Higher order mode parasitic band. Effect of the position of iris 1 and 2 (iris 4 and 5).

Actually, the attenuation of the higher order mode parasitic band obtained in Fig. 13 is quite good. This is because iris 1 and 2 (4 and 5) are already close to the cavity center ($p_1 = p_2 = 3$ mm). However, as shown in Fig. 15, passing from $p_1 = p_2 = 3$ mm to $p_1 = p_2 = 1.6$ mm, the parasitic band attenuation passes from about 25 dB to about 30 dB.

The four pole TM cavity filter structure with wide spurious free range is shown in Fig. 16a and its response is shown in Fig. 16b. This has been obtained after further optimization. The iris resonances have been suppressed up to 25 dB and higher order mode spurious frequencies has been suppressed up to 33 dB. The iris resonances (iris 2 & 4) initially present in Fig. 13 around 12.2 GHz are now present at 10.65 GHz in Fig. 16b.

Fig. 16. TM cavity filter. (a) Filter configuration. (b) S parameters response with wide spurious free range.

This frequency shift is because iris width w_2 has been increased (decreasing p_2) during the optimization process for increasing the higher order mode parasitic band attenuation. As demonstrated in Fig. 14b, this is a trade-off between achieving better higher order mode suppression and getting iris resonance close to the passband.

An important aspect of TM filters is the presence of the TZs. It is then important to understand what happens to the TZs when the spurious self-suppression method is applied. According to [28], each TM resonator is potentially capable of a TZ that is generated by exploiting the non-resonating mode TE_{101} for transporting some power that bypasses the resonant mode TM_{110} . Here in the following, we resume a few very simple rules regarding the TZs in TM cavities [28]:

- 1) A TM cavity having input and output irises orthogonally placed does not allow the TE_{101} mode to bypass the cavity and it does not generate a TZ.
- 2) The closer the iris to the cavity center, the higher the excitation of the TE_{101} . A higher excitation of TE_{101} results in a TZ closer to the passband.
- 3) If in a cavity, irises are both above (or both below) the cavity center, the TZ generated by the cavity is in the lower stopband.
- 4) If in a cavity, irises are one above and the other below the cavity center, the TZ generated by the cavity is in the upper stopband.

Rules n. 3 and 4 are a consequence of the change of sign of the coupling to the TM_{110} mode when the position of one of the two irises passes from above to below the cavity center [28].

According to classical TM filter configuration of Fig. 8a, all irises are aligned. This result in a number of TZs equal to the number of cavities. According to Fig. 9a, when the classical spurious suppression method is applied, each cavity has irises orthogonally positioned. According to the rule n. 1, this results in no TZs. This can be clearly seen in Fig. 9b where no TZs are present close to the filter band. According to Fig. 16a, when the proposed spurious self-suppression is applied, the two central cavities have irises orthogonally positioned, losing the capability of generating the bypass coupling in the two central cavities. In terms of routing scheme, this means that the coupling between NRN A and B (as well as B and C) is equal to zero when the spurious self-suppression method is applied. In all other cavities irises are instead aligned and the bypass coupling is maintained. This results in a number of TZs equal to $N-2$, where N is the number of cavities (corresponding to the filter order). This means that for the fourth order filter of Fig. 16a two TZs are expected. Furthermore, considering that input and output irises in the first cavity (corresponding to iris 1 and iris 2 of the filter) and in the last cavity (corresponding to iris 4 and iris 5 of the filter) are all placed in the same side with respect to the cavity center, according to the rule n. 3, the two TZs must be placed in the lower stopband. Finally, considering that the first and last cavity are identical, the two TZs are positioned exactly at

the same frequency [28] thus resulting in a double TZ. This can be clearly seen in Fig. 16b.

Fig. 17a shows instead the antisymmetric configuration, where irises in the left part of the filter are all below the cavity center while those in the right part of the filter are all above the cavity center. In practice, this configuration has been obtained by rotating the first cavity (together with the relevant irises and feeding waveguide) of 180 deg. around the filter longitudinal axes. The response is plotted in Fig. 17b and as expected, the double TZ is still placed in the lower stopband, however the response shows that the level of spike at 10.65 GHz has been slightly improved to 32 dB. For comparison purpose, the response of the classical filter already shown in Fig. 8c has been also included. The narrowband response comparison of the filter passband is shown in Fig. 18 along with the final optimized filter dimensions.

It is worth nothing that, according to the rule n.2, a fine control of the position of the TZs is possible by increasing/decreasing the distance of the irises (except the central one) from the cavity center. This is clearly shown in Fig. 14b, where different responses with different position of the TZs are shown as a function of p_1 and p_2 . Of course, the fine positioning is limited by the exigency of having p_1 and p_2 small as required by the spurious self-suppression. This means that it is not possible to put TZs very far away from the filter band.

Fig. 17. Four-pole TM cavity filter with antisymmetric geometry. (a) 3-D view. (b) Comparison between the response of the classical four-pole TM cavity filter and the proposed filter.

Fig. 18. Final dimensions of the filter. $w_1=15.4$ mm, $h_1=3.2$ mm, $w_2=14.15$ mm, $h_2=2.6$ mm, $w_3=6.75$ mm, $h_3=1.25$ mm, $p_1=1.6$ mm, $p_2=1.6$ mm, $p_x=7$ mm, $w_{c1}=23.13$ mm, $h_{c1}=23.265$ mm, $w_{c2}=22.83$ mm, $h_{c2}=22.7$ mm. The thickness of the coupling slots is 0.5 mm.

Beside the precise positioning, it is also possible to change the TZ position from the lower to the upper stopband. This can be done by exploiting the rule n. 4, leading to the structure of Fig. 19a. As shown in Fig. 19b, with this configuration the double TZs passes from the lower to the upper stopband, thus improving the filter selectivity in the upper part of the band. The additional spikes appearing at 17.4 GHz, 18 GHz and 19.3 GHz that reaches the level of -17 dB, are due to the higher order modes present in the coupling irises (TE_{20}) and cavity mode (TM_{220}). However, those spikes are extremely narrowband, and they are visible only because no losses have been considered in the simulation. When metal losses (aluminum) were considered, the spikes almost disappear, as can be seen in the response of Fig. 19c. According to the

Fig. 19. TM cavity filter. a) Final configuration. (b) S parameters response. (c) S_{21} response of the four-pole filter by considering aluminum as a lossy metal.

author experience, the simulation of filters with aluminum losses represents quite well the losses in silverplated manufactured filter. Indeed, in manufactured filters, additional sources of losses are present (e.g., roughness, assembling connections etc).

B. 6th Order Filter

In order to demonstrate that spurious self-suppression procedure can be also applied to higher order filters, the design of a six-pole TM cavity filter fed by the standard *wr-90* waveguide, centered at 9.2 GHz having FBW of 1.5% is here reported. For comparison purpose, in Fig. 20 the classical TM filter is shown. In particular, Fig. 20a shows the classical 6 pole TM geometry. Fig. 20b shows the routing scheme including filter passband (TM_{110}) with NRNs, filter parasitic band due to higher order modes (TM_{120}), and filter parasitic band due to coupling iris resonances (TE_{10}) mode. Fig. 20c shows instead the classical TM filter response with parasitic bands.

Analogously to what happens in the 4th order filter, iris 1 and iris 7 resonances are not resonating in the same band of the other irises. This means that only 5 resonances are visible in the iris parasitic band positioned around 11-12 GHz. This can be seen in Fig. 20c, where 3 RZs positioned in the upper part plus two ‘fused’ RZs positioned in the lower part of the iris parasitic band are clearly visible.

Fig. 20. Classical 6-pole TM cavity. a) 3-D view. (b) Routing scheme including filter band and two parasitic bands. (c) Wideband S-parameter response. Figure inset shows the filter band.

Similarly, to what has been already done with 4th order filters, the steps described in Section IV.A have also been applied to the 6th order filters. This consists in the central iris orthogonally positioned far away from the cavity center and all other irises positioned close to the cavity center. After the application of the spurious suppression method, the number of TZs is equal to the filter order minus 2. This leads to 4 TZs in case of 6th order filter. In order to show the flexibility in the positioning of TZs, two 6th order filter with spurious free band up to 20 GHz has been successfully designed.

The first design of the proposed 6-pole TM cavity filter with spurious self-suppression method is presented in Fig. 21a. In this case, a double TZ is positioned in the lower and the other in the upper stopband. Indeed, according to the rules illustrated

Fig. 21. 6-pole TM cavity filter configuration. (a) 3-D view. (b) Wideband response with TZs below and above passband.

during the design of the 4th order filter, cavity 1 produces a TZ in the lower stopband (as well as cavity 6), while cavity 2 produces a TZ in the upper stopband (as well as cavity 5). Filter response is shown in Fig. 21b.

The second design is shown in Fig. 22. As can be seen from Fig. 22a, all cavities capable of a TZ (cavity 1, 2, 5 and 6) are designed to produce TZs in the upper stopband. This is because all those cavities have irises with alternate position with respect to the cavity center. In particular, because of the symmetry of the structure, cavity 1 and 6 produces a TZ in the same position, as well as cavity 2 and 5. This leads to a couple of double TZs in the upper stopband. Actually, in Fig. 22b the response shows that the double TZ at higher frequency has split into two close TZs. This is because NRNs have not been used here and there are some perturbations that can split double TZ [28], [33], [34].

Fig. 22. 6-pole TM cavity filter. (a) 3-D view. (b) Wideband response.

Results show that iris spurious frequency level is -30 dB, higher order modes spurious frequency level is -24 dB, whereas stopband has been increased to 20 GHz. Iris 4 now resonates at 20 GHz along with other not suppressed higher order modes present in the cavity. Fig. 23 shows the final dimensions of the filter.

Two additional spikes at 17.728 GHz and 18.253 GHz due to higher order modes present in the coupling irises (TE₂₀) and cavity mode (TM₂₂₀) are also present. Similarly, to that of the 4th order filter, such spikes are extremely narrowband and practically disappear when metal losses are included. This is clearly shown in Fig. 24, where the simulated response includes the metal losses (aluminum).

Fig. 23. Final dimensions for the 6th order filter. $w_1=14.56$ mm, $h_1=3.15$ mm, $w_2=13.48$ mm, $h_2=2.65$ mm, $w_3=13.45$ mm, $h_3=2.5$ mm, $w_4=6.95$ mm, $h_4=1.25$, $p_1=-1.56$ mm, $p_2=1.56$ mm, $p_3=-1.56$ mm, $p_x=7.5$ mm, $w_{c1}=23.7$ mm, $h_{c1}=22.2$ mm, $w_{c2}=23.7$ mm, $h_{c2}=22.2$ mm, $w_{c3}=23.7$ mm, $h_{c3}=22.2$ mm. The thickness of the coupling slots is 0.5 mm. The length of the resonators is 5 mm.

Fig. 24. Response of the filter in Fig. 22 including losses (aluminum).

V. MEASUREMENT OF THE PROPOSED SIXTH ORDER TM CAVITY FILTER

In order to show the feasibility of the proposed approach, the 6th order filter has been manufactured and measured. Photographs of the assembled filter and disassembled filter are shown in Fig. 25a and Fig. 25b, respectively. One tuning screw of radius 1 mm is inserted in each cavity for the tuning of the resonance frequencies. No tuning screws for the coupling have been used. To support the manufacturing process, sharp corners of cavities and irises have been changed into rounded corners. The thickness of the coupling slot is 0.5 mm, this contributes to maintain the filter very compact. Fig. 26 shows the comparison between simulated and measured response in the range of the passband. A slight frequency shift is present between measurement and simulation. The in-band return loss is 14 dB in the measured results, while it is 23 dB in the simulation. This difference is probably due to the manufacturing tolerances. It should be noted that the theoretical Q-factor of the final cavity considering aluminum as a lossy metal is about 3900. This corresponds to a realistic value of 2700 considering an efficiency of 70%. This leads to an insertion loss of 0.9 dB. The measured insertion loss is 1.4 dB. Of course, the filter performance can be improved by using post processing techniques such as brazing, silverplating etc. Some of such techniques have already been successfully applied to this kind of filters [38], [39]. However, this is beyond the scope of the paper that consists in demonstrating that the theory of the spurious self-suppression works, and it is applicable to real filters. This is well demonstrated by Fig. 27 where the wideband measured response of the filter is compared with the simulated response. Measurements are in good agreement with the simulations.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 25. Prototypes of 6-pole TM cavity filter (a) Assembled. (b) Disassembled.

Fig. 26. In-band response of the of the six-pole filter. Comparison between simulated and measured results.

Fig. 27. Wideband response of the 6th order filter. Comparison between measured and simulated response.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a new technique called spurious self-suppression method has been introduced. In contrast to the classical approach for suppressing higher order modes, where all couplings to spurious resonances are minimized as much as possible, the proposed strategy is instead based on a different approach. It is indeed shown that better results are obtained, when only the central coupling to the spurious resonances are minimized whereas all others are maximized.

In order to demonstrate the practical applicability of such a technique, this method has been used for increasing the out-of-band behavior of TM cavity filters of even order.

The practical application of self-suppression method to TM filters consists in three actions: 1) all irises are oriented in the same direction except the central one that is instead orthogonally positioned with respect to all others. 2) the central iris is positioned far away from the cavity center. 3) all other irises are positioned close to the cavity center. By following those very simple rules, a 4th and 6th order TM cavity filters centered at 9.2 GHz have been successfully designed with a spurious free band up to 20 GHz.

The 6th order filter has been manufactured and measured. Measurements confirms the wide spurious free band up to 20 GHz, thus demonstrating the feasibility of the proposed approach.

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